

Welcome to the online survey for persons affiliated to NFDI member organisations!

Technopolis has been commissioned to evaluate Base4NFDI. As you are aware, Base4NFDI is a joint initiative of all NFDI consortia to create shared basic services that can be used by potentially all consortia.

The aim of this survey is to gather insights from persons affiliated to NFDI member organisations on Base4NFDI.

The survey covers topics such as the project structure, processes for identifying and discussing basic services, your assessment of the submission and evaluation processes for basic services, activities for the deployment of basic services and your evaluation of the relevance of the project.

Completing the survey will take approximately 20–30 minutes. If needed, you can pause and continue later - your progress will be saved in this browser. Your responses will be used exclusively in an anonymised and aggregated form.

Please complete the questionnaire by April 22nd.

Your perspectives and experiences are crucial for assessing and further developing Base4NFDI. Your input will be a key component of the evaluation report.

In addition to this online survey, further data collection activities will be conducted, including another online survey with the developer teams of basic services, document analyses, interviews, as well as focus groups and workshops.

If you have any questions regarding this survey, please feel free to contact us at dominik.obeth@technopolis-group.com.

We sincerely appreciate your valuable support!

Section A: Survey respondents' affiliations & background

Disclaimer: Although this survey is generally anonymous, we ask a few questions that, if answered, might potentially de-anonymise you. However, all responses will only be reported in an aggregated manner by Technopolis, ensuring that no individual can be traced back. All individual data can only be accessed by Technopolis and will be treated confidentially.

Mandatory questions are marked with an asterisk (*).

A1.

A2. Is your institution part of the NFDI consortium ?

The consortium named in the question above is the one which distributed the present questionnaire to you. It is however possible that your organisation is not part of that consortium. If your institution is a member of multiple consortia, please choose the consortium from which you received this survey link invitation. Member institutions of NFDI consortia can be applicant institutions, co-applicants or participants.

Yes

No

A3. Is your institution part of any other NFDI consortia?

Choose one of the following answers. If your institution is part of multiple consortia, please choose the consortium for which you would like to answer the survey questions. Member institutions of NFDI consortia could be applicant institutions, co-applicants or participants.

BERD@NFDI KonsortSWD NFDI4Culture NFDI4Memory NFDI4Objects Text+ NFDI4DataScience NFDI4Energy NFDI4Ing NFDI-MatWerk NFDIxCS DataPLANT FAIRagro NFDI4Immuno GHGA NFDI4Biodiversity NFDI4BIOIMAGE NFDI4Health NFDI4Microbiota DAPHNE4NFDI FAIRmat

A4. To which NFDI member institution do you belong?

Choose one of the following answers

acatech – Deutsche Akademie der Technikwissenschaften e.V.

AG CAA e.V.

Akademie der Wissenschaften Hamburg

Akademie der Wissenschaften und der Literatur Mainz

Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Göttingen

Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg

Alfred-Wegener-Institut – Helmholtz Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung

Archäologische Staatssammlung

Archivschule Marburg – Hochschule für Archivwissenschaft

Bach-Archiv Leipzig

Bauhaus-Universität Weimar

Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften

Bayerische Staatsbibliothek

Bayerisches Staatsministerium für Wissenschaft und Kunst

Behörde für Wissenschaft, Forschung und Gleichstellung Hamburg

Bergische Universität Wuppertal

Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften (BBAW)

Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) gGmbH

Brandenburgische Technische Universität Cottbus-Senftenberg

Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie

Section B: Internal structure and responsibilities of Base4NFDI

B1.

B2. Are you aware of the project Base4NFDI in general?

Choose one of the following answer. Answering 'No' will directly take you to the end of the survey.

Yes

No

B3. Are you generally aware of how Base4NFDI is structured internally to support basic service development?

Choose one of the following answers. Internal structures refer, for example, to the Task Areas, Service Stewards, and Section Liaison Officers.

Yes, definitely

Somewhat

Not really

No, not at all

No answer

B4. Have you personally ever been in contact with someone from the Base4NFDI team?

Choose one of the following answers. The Base4NFDI team includes Task Areas 1-4 as well as the Service Stewards.

Yes

No

Don't know

No answer

B7. Are there any other comments or suggestions for improvement regarding the internal structure of Base4NFDI that you would like to point out?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

Section C: Process for discussing and identifying potential basic service candidates in the sections

The NFDI sections form the starting point for identifying and discussing potential basic services before proposal submissions to Base4NFDI are drafted. The following questions focus on the identification and discussion processes of potential basic services within the sections, including decision-making in the sections on their support before proposals are written and submitted to Base4NFDI.

C1. Have you personally been active in one of the following sections of the NFDI (e.g. in a section’s working group)?

Select all that apply

- Common Infrastructures (section-infra)
- Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects (section-ELSA)
- (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance (section-metadata)
- Industry Engagement (section-industry)
- Training & Education (section-edutrain)
- No, I am not active in any of the NFDI sections
- Don't know
- No answer

C2. Have you been involved in discussions about potential basic services and / or decision-making about supporting these potential basic services in the sections or working groups (e.g. in a section meeting or in a working group)?

Choose one of the following answers

Yes

No

Don't know

No answer

C3. How would you assess the discussion and identification processes for potential basic services in the NFDI sections?

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the respective statements.

	Fully agree	Mostly agree	Partly agree / partly disagree	Mostly disagree	Fully disagree	Don't know
The discussions are generally fair and inclusive, allowing all voices to be heard.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My consortium's needs for basic services are in general adequately represented in the discussions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The needs for basic services for my institution are in general adequately represented in the discussions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In general, my personal opinion has been heard in the discussions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C4. Would you like to further elaborate on the answer(s) from the previous question?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

C5. Do you have any feedback on the process for identifying, discussing, and submitting potential basic services that you would like to highlight or suggest improvements for?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

Section D: Submission process for basic services at Base4NFDI

The following questions refer to processes regarding the submission of basic services to Base4NFDI. We refer to the submission (process) as all actions related to writing and submitting a basic service proposal to Base4NFDI for any of the three development phases (initialisation, integration, ramping-up), including re-submissions.

D1. Have you been part of a team submitting one or multiple basic service proposals to Base4NFDI?

Select all that apply

Yes, for the initialisation phase (first phase, including re-submissions)

Yes, for the integration phase (second phase)

No

Don't know / No answer

D2. Has/have the submission(s) been accepted for funding?

Including re-submissions. Choose one of the following answers

Yes, all of them

Yes, some of them

No

Don't know

No answer

D3. To what extent would you agree with the following statements about the submission process for a basic service to Base4NFDI?

	Fully agree	Mostly agree	Partly agree / partly disagree	Mostly disagree	Fully disagree	Don't know
The submission process for a basic service is clearly structured.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
All necessary information regarding the submission process is readily available.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sufficient support is provided to applicants throughout the submission process.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The submission process is sufficiently fast.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The submission process for basic services is flexible enough to accommodate specific needs or unique circumstances of different ideas for basic services.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

D4.

If you look at the processes for identifying basic services in the sections and the submission process for basic services, how do you personally consider the relative influence of the various actors involved?

	Too much say	Adequate say	Too little say	No say	Don't know
Sections	<input type="checkbox"/>				

	Too much say	Adequate say	Too little say	No say	Don't know
Consortium spokespersons	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Consortium member institutions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Technical Expert Committee	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Base4NFDI team	<input type="checkbox"/>				
NFDI scientific senate	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Infrastructure organisations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Researchers from universities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Researchers from research institutes (Max Planck, Leibniz etc)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section E: Evaluation process (Technical Expert Committee, TEC)

We refer to the evaluation process as the entire process involved in evaluating basic service proposals at Base4NFDI. This includes the assessment and review of basic service submissions by the Technical Expert Committee (TEC), discussions and decisions about basic services within the consortia, as well as discussions, votes, and decisions made in the consortia assembly regarding basic services.

E1. Are you generally aware of the TEC and its role in the evaluation process?

Choose one of the following answers

Yes

Yes, somewhat

No

No answer

E2.

To what extent would you agree with the following statements about the evaluation processes for basic services conducted by Base4NFDI together with the Technical Expert Committee (TEC)?

Fully agree Mostly agree Partly agree / partly disagree Mostly disagree Fully disagree Don't know

The criteria applied by the TEC for evaluating basic service submissions are transparent and well-communicated.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								
The recommendations of the TEC regarding the evaluation of basic service submissions are generally fair.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								
The evaluation process conducted by Base4NFDI together with the TEC demonstrates subject-matter expertise.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								
The published reasons for decisions (e.g., acceptance, rejection, required revisions, or budget reductions) are communicated clearly and are understandable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								
The personnel composition of the TEC is adequate to evaluate the technical aspects of the various proposed services effectively.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								

E3. Do you want to specify your answer(s) to the previous question? (e.g. How could the process be improved? What aspects are working particularly well?)

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

Always Frequently Sometimes Rarely Never Don't know

Decisions are made by a designated set of experts on a given topic	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Decisions are made by (almost) all consortium members, but no formal voting process is conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Decisions are made by (almost) all consortium members, and a formal voting process is conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>					

F3. Who is involved in discussions about basic service submissions before deciding on an submission's support?

Choose one of the following answers

There is no discussion in general	<input type="checkbox"/>
Discussions are generally held in small informal circles	<input type="checkbox"/>
Discussions take place within a designated body (e.g. a board or an expert committee on the topic)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Discussion take place with many or (almost) all consortium members	<input type="checkbox"/>
No answer	<input type="checkbox"/>

F4. Would you like to mention any other aspects regarding the processes of opinion formation, discussion and decision-making in the consortia?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

F5. Have you participated in a meeting of the consortia assembly?

Optional. Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, in my function as consortium spokesperson
- No
- Don't know
- No answer
- Yes, in another function:

Yes, in another function:

F6. In your opinion, are the quorum requirements for approving funding for basic service development in the consortia assembly adequate?

The required quora to approve funding for the development of basic services in the consortia assembly are 25% for the initialisation phase, 50% for the integration phase, and 75% for the ramping-up phase.

	Too high	Adequate	Too low	Don't know
Support of 25 % of the consortia for funding in the first phase (initialisation)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Support of 50 % of the consortia for funding in the second phase (integration)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Support of 75 % of the consortia for funding in the third phase (ramping-up)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

F7. In your opinion, is the three-stage process adequate? What changes, if any, would you propose?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German. The three stages are initialisation, integration and ramping-up.

Section G: Evaluation process (overall)

The following questions refer to the evaluation process overall.

G1.

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the evaluation processes for a basic service to Base4NFDI, overall?

Fully agree Mostly agree Partly agree / partly disagree Mostly disagree Fully disagree Don't know

The evaluation process for basic service candidates is generally fair.

.....

The evaluation process generally accounts adequately for the needs and requirements of the consortia.

.....

The evaluation process generally contributes to a sustainable deployment and usage of basic services in the long run.

.....

G2. If you look at the processes for evaluating of basic services at Base4NFDI overall, how do you personally consider the relative influence of the various actors involved?

Too much say Adequate say Too little say No say Don't know

Consortium spokespersons

.....

Consortium member institutions

.....

	Too much say	Adequate say	Too little say	No say	Don't know
Technical Expert Committee	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Base4NFDI team	<input type="checkbox"/>				
NFDI scientific senate	<input type="checkbox"/>				

G3. Are there any other comments or suggestions for improvement regarding the submission and evaluation processes for basic services that you would like to point out?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

Section H: Activities for service deployment and collaboration between actors and stakeholders

H1. In which of the following activities have you already taken part as a participant?

Select all that apply

- Networking events or activities (e.g., fostering collaborations or creating connections with relevant stakeholders in the consortia)
- Service Roadshows
- Base4NFDI User Conference (UC4B)
- Demos/Presentations/Lectures about basic services
- Interactive formats (Workshops, Q&A, trainings, hands-on sessions)
- Interactive meetings/conferences/workshops with EOSC stakeholders

Meetings/conferences/workshops with EOSC stakeholders

No answer

H2. Overall, how helpful did you find these activities?

	Very helpful	Rather helpful	Partly helpful / partly not helpful	Rather not helpful	Not helpful at all	Don't know
Networking events or activities (e.g., fostering collaborations or creating connections with relevant stakeholders in the consortia).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Service Roadshows	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Base4NFDI User Conference (UC4B)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Demos/Presentations/Lectures about basic services	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interactive formats (Workshops, Q&A, trainings, hands-on sessions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interactive meetings/conferences/workshops with EOSC stakeholders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Meetings/conferences/workshops with EOSC stakeholders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

H3. Are there any activities you wish for, but, to your knowledge, have not been carried out yet?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

H4. To what extent would you agree with the following statements?

The Base4NFDI team consists of the member of the task areas, the section liaison officers and the service stewards

Fully agree Mostly agree Partly agree / partly disagree Mostly disagree Fully disagree Don't know

The communication between my consortium and the Base4NFDI team is effective and timely.

The Base4NFDI team is responsive to questions, requests and feedback of my consortium.

The Base4NFDI Team supports my consortium in articulating our requirements and needs regarding the development of basic services.

Overall, I am satisfied with the collaboration with the Base4NFDI team and my consortium.

H5. What specific improvements, if any, would you suggest to enhance the collaboration and communication between your consortium and the Base4NFDI team?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

H6. Regarding the collaboration between your consortium and the developer teams of each basic service: Please indicate approximately to how many basic service developer teams the following statements apply:

1-2 basic services 3-4 basic services 5-6 basic services 7-8 basic services Don't know

Our consortium closely cooperates with the developer team to communicate our needs and concerns.

Our feedback is effectively considered and incorporated into the development of the basic service.

We provide clear and binding commitments on how we plan to integrate the basic service into our consortium.

1-2 basic services	3-4 basic services	5-6 basic services	7-8 basic services	Don't know
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Our consortium actively supports the developer team in promoting the basic service to ensure its adoption and usability.

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
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Our consortium ensures that our requirements and use cases are clearly communicated to align with the basic service being developed.

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
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The collaboration between our consortium and the developer team is productive and beneficial for deploying the basic service.

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
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H7. Would you like to specify your answer from the previous question?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

H8. What specific improvements, if any, would you suggest to enhance the collaboration between your consortium and the developer teams? If your collaboration is of different quality between services, please specify here.

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

H9. Are there any aspects you would like to mention regarding the collaboration with the Base4NFDI team?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

Section I: Relevance of Base4NFDI for the community

**I1. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
IAM4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**I2. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
PID4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**I3. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
TS4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**I4. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
Jupyter4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**I5. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
DMP4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**I6. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
KGI4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**I7. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
nfdi.software**

Please select all that apply.

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**I8. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
RDMTraining4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

19. From your personal perspective, how likely is it that your institution will make use of the following services?

	Very likely	Rather likely	Rather unlikely	Very unlikely	Don't know
IAM4NFDI	<input type="checkbox"/>				
PID4NFDI	<input type="checkbox"/>				
TS4NFDI	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Jupyter4NFDI	<input type="checkbox"/>				
DMP4NFDI	<input type="checkbox"/>				
KGI4NFDI	<input type="checkbox"/>				
nfdi.software	<input type="checkbox"/>				
RDMTraining4NFDI	<input type="checkbox"/>				

110. What are, in your opinion, the main reasons your institution is (rather) unlikely to adopt this service?

IAM4NFDI

Please select all that apply.

- Our institution does not need this service.
- The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our institution.
- The service proposal is not convincing.
- The service is not interoperable with other services we use.
- Implementing the service is too costly.
- We already have a comparable service in operation.
- We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

Other reasons

I11. What are, in your opinion, the main reasons your institution is (rather) unlikely to adopt this service?
PID4NFDI

Please select all that apply.

Our institution does not need this service.

The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our institution.

The service proposal is not convincing.

The service is not interoperable with other services we use.

Implementing the service is too costly.

We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

Other reasons

I12. What are, in your opinion, the main reasons your institution is (rather) unlikely to adopt this service?
TS4NFDI

Please select all that apply.

Our institution does not need this service.

The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our institution.

The service proposal is not convincing.

The service is not interoperable with other services we use.

Implementing the service is too costly.

We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

Other reasons

**I13. What are, in your opinion, the main reasons your institution is (rather) unlikely to adopt this service?
Jupyter4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

Our institution does not need this service.

The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our institution.

The service proposal is not convincing.

The service is not interoperable with other services we use.

Implementing the service is too costly.

We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

Other reasons

I14. What are, in your opinion, the main reasons your institution is (rather) unlikely to adopt this service?

DMP4NFDI

Please select all that apply.

- Our institution does not need this service.
- The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our institution.
- The service proposal is not convincing.
- The service is not interoperable with other services we use.
- Implementing the service is too costly.
- We already have a comparable service in operation.
- We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.
- There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.
- The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.
- Other reasons

I15. What are, in your opinion, the main reasons your institution is (rather) unlikely to adopt this service?

KGI4NFDI

Please select all that apply.

- Our institution does not need this service.
- The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our institution.
- The service proposal is not convincing.
- The service is not interoperable with other services we use.
- Implementing the service is too costly.
- We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

Other reasons

**I16. What are, in your opinion, the main reasons your institution is (rather) unlikely to adopt this service?
nfdi.software**

Please select all that apply.

Our institution does not need this service.

The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our institution.

The service proposal is not convincing.

The service is not interoperable with other services we use.

Implementing the service is too costly.

We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

Other reasons

**I17. What are, in your opinion, the main reasons your institution is (rather) unlikely to adopt this service?
RDMTraining4NFDI**

Please select all that apply.

Our institution does not need this service.

The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our institution.

The service proposal is not convincing.

The service is not interoperable with other services we use.

Implementing the service is too costly.

We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

Other reasons

I18. For the following services you have indicated as useful for your institution, your consortium has, however, NOT declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

PID4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
TS4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
Jupyter4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
DMP4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
KGI4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
nfdi.software	<input type="text"/>
RDMTraining4NFDI	<input type="text"/>

I19. For the following services you have indicated as NOT useful for your institution, your consortium has, however, declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

IAM4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
PID4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
TS4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
Jupyter4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
DMP4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
KGI4NFDI	<input type="text"/>
nfdi.software	<input type="text"/>
RDMTraining4NFDI	<input type="text"/>

I20. For the following services you have indicated as useful for your consortium, your consortium has, however, NOT declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.
PID4NFDI

Please select all that apply

- Our consortium does not need this service.
- The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our consortium.
- The service proposal is not convincing.
- The service is not interoperable with other services we use.
- Implementing the service is too costly.
- We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

I21. For the following services you have indicated as useful for your consortium, your consortium has, however, NOT declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.
TS4NFDI

Please select all that apply

Our consortium does not need this service.

The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our consortium.

The service proposal is not convincing.

The service is not interoperable with other services we use.

Implementing the service is too costly.

We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

I22. For the following services you have indicated as useful for your consortium, your consortium has, however, NOT declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.
Jupyter4NFDI

Please select all that apply

Our consortium does not need this service.

The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our consortium.

The service proposal is not convincing.

- The service is not interoperable with other services we use.
- Implementing the service is too costly.
- We already have a comparable service in operation.
- We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.
- There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.
- The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

I23. For the following services you have indicated as useful for your consortium, your consortium has, however, **NOT declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.**
DMP4NFDI

Please select all that apply

- Our consortium does not need this service.
- The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our consortium.
- The service proposal is not convincing.
- The service is not interoperable with other services we use.
- Implementing the service is too costly.
- We already have a comparable service in operation.
- We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.
- There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.
- The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

I24. For the following services you have indicated as useful for your consortium, your consortium has, however, NOT declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.
KGI4NFDI

Please select all that apply

- Our consortium does not need this service.
- The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our consortium.
- The service proposal is not convincing.
- The service is not interoperable with other services we use.
- Implementing the service is too costly.
- We already have a comparable service in operation.
- We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.
- There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.
- The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

I25. For the following services you have indicated as useful for your consortium, your consortium has, however, NOT declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.
nfdi.software

Please select all that apply

- Our consortium does not need this service.
- The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our consortium.
- The service proposal is not convincing.
- The service is not interoperable with other services we use.
- Implementing the service is too costly.
- We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

I26. For the following services you have indicated as useful for your consortium, your consortium has, however, NOT declared its support for this basic service in the consortia assembly. Please specify why you think this is the case.
RDMTraining4NFDI

Please select all that apply

Our consortium does not need this service.

The service is too general and does not meet the specific needs of our consortium.

The service proposal is not convincing.

The service is not interoperable with other services we use.

Implementing the service is too costly.

We already have a comparable service in operation.

We lack the resources or expertise to implement the service.

There is insufficient support or guidance available for implementing the service.

The long-term sustainability of the service is unclear.

I27. From your perspective, does it make sense that basic services are being developed through community-driven co-design across NFDI consortia?

Choose one of the following answers

- Fully agree
- Rather agree
- Partly agree / partly disagree
- Rather disagree
- Fully disagree
- Don't know / No answer

I28. You (rather) disagreed in the previous question. What would be an alternative approach in your opinion?

Optional

I29. When you look at all services that have been granted funding by Base4NFDI, are there any gaps, i.e. basic services that would be needed, but are not yet being developed?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

J3. How do the services developed under Base4NFDI address the FAIR principles? Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Fully agree	Mostly agree	Partly agree / partly disagree	Mostly disagree	Fully disagree	Don't know
The developed services improve the findability of data and resources in the NFDI community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The developed services improve the accessibility of data and resources in the NFDI community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The developed services improve the interoperability of data and resources in the NFDI community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The developed services improve the reusability of data and resources in the NFDI community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

J4. Are there any other aspects that you would like to mention regarding your overall satisfaction with Base4NFDI?

Optional. You can answer in English or German.

Section K: Personal questions

Please note: The following final questions may potentially de-anonymise you. We guarantee you, however, that all responses will only be reported in an aggregated manner, ensuring that no individuals can be traced back.

K1. What position do you have in your institution?

Choose one of the following answers.

Executive Leadership (Managing Director, Executive Board, Director-General)

Senior Management (Head of Department, Division Director)

Project Management (Project Lead, Programme Manager)

Specialist / Research Staff (Researcher, Analyst, Engineer)

No answer

Other:

Other:

K2. As part of the evaluation, we plan to conduct additional interviews and focus groups to explore specific aspects of Base4NFDI. Would you be generally available to participate in an interview/focus group?

Please indicate your email address (optional)

I'm not available

Yes, I'm available under the following email address

Yes, I'm available under the following email address

Your responses have been saved.

We will conduct in-depth interviews and additional workshops based on the survey results, with the evaluation concluding in August.

Thank you for your valuable support! You may close this survey now.